

THE IMPORTANCE OF INSTRUCTIONAL METHODS IN THE TEACHING PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

This article provides ideas on the importance of the use of training methods in the educational process.

The categories of purpose, content, form reveal the essence of the educational process (what it is aimed at, what it fills, what it is directed at, in what form it is completed). However, there is also another important category related to the question of how to educate in highlighting the essence of instructing. This is a concept of the instructional method.

The method of instructing (Greek "metodos" – path) is the way to achieve the goal of educating somebody. When applied to the schooling practice, methods are ways to influence the mind, will, feelings and behavior of those who are brought up.

Purpose and content of instructional methods. The method will not be positive and negative, it is impossible to assess a certain path in the instructing process as highly effective and ineffective. The effectiveness of the method can be assessed from the point of view of the conditions in which it is applied.

The purposeful choice of instructional methods depends on a number of factors.

1. Goals and objectives of instructing. The goal not only justifies the methods, but also clarifies them. Whatever the goal is, it is necessary that the methods of achieving it to be in accordance with it.

2. Educational content. It should be noted that exactly one task can be filled with different thoughts. Therefore, it is extremely important to associate methods not with content at all, but with a clear opinion.

3. Taking into account the age characteristics of the Breeders. These or similar tasks are solved in connection with the age of the upbringing. Age is simply not an indicator of how much he lived. The level of development of acquired social experience, psychological and moral qualities is reflected in it. Suppose that a sense of responsibility can also be formed in students studying in primary education, secondary education and secondary specialized,

vocational education institutions. However, at each stage, different methods are used in terms of the formation of this quality.

4. The level of formation of the team. In connection with the development of the team form of self-government, the methods of pedagogical influence also do not remain unchanged. As we know, the flexibility of management is a necessary condition for the competent cooperation of the educator with the educators.

5. Individual peculiarities of the upbringing. Common methods, common programs themselves, cannot be the basis of educational interaction. It is necessary to fix them individual and personal. A humane educator tries to apply techniques that allow each individual to develop identity, maintain identity, realize his "I".

6. Educational conditions. Relationships that arise to him in the classroom beyond material, psychophysiological, sanitary-hygienic: climate in the team, method of pedagogical leadership, etc tegishlidir. Ma there will be no abstract conditions, they are always clear. Their fusion is visible in specific cases. Conditions in which upbringing increases amalgam received the name of pedagogical situations.

7. Means of upbringing. Methods of upbringing are formed by means of upbringing, which arise as components of the upbringing process. Methods are firmly connected with them, and there are other means of upbringing that can be enslaved together. Examples include visual manuals, visual arts and musical arts, media, which provide essential support for the effective application of techniques.

8. The degree of mastery of pedagogical qualifications. The educator usually chooses only those techniques that he knows and occupies the application. Since many methods are complex, it requires the use of a lot of force on the woodpecker. Educators who evade such responsibility try to organize activities without them. The result will be less effective than using methods based on different images, different goals, tasks, conditions.

9. Upbringing time. When there is little time and the goal is large, "strong driving" methods are used, and under favorable conditions, "deviating" methods of upbringing are used. The division of upbringing into "strong driving" and "deviant" methods is conditional: the first is associated with reprimand and coercion, the second with exhortation and constant teaching.

10. Expected result. When choosing a method, the educator must have confidence that he will achieve the right. To do this, it is necessary to know in advance what result the method being used will lead to.

3. Classification of training methods

In modern pedagogy, there are dozens of educational classifications, some of which reflect the solution of practical tasks, some only theoretical ones. Methods are divided into persuasion, exercise, stimulation and reprimand according to their specific character. In this case, the general characteristic sign of the method reflects orientation, originality, suitability for application. This classification is strongly accompanied by general methods of upbringing, which are characterized by a greater generalization of methods. It covers methods of persuasion, Organization of activities, stimulation of the behavior of students. I.S. In Marenko's classification, parenting techniques groups are named as follows: explanatory-reproductive, problematic situational, teaching and exercise techniques, stimulating,

obstructing, managing, self-discipline. Methods can be divided into two groups based on the results of their influence on the upbringing:

1. Moral norms, influencing the formation of motives, the formation of imagination, understanding, ideas.
2. Influencing the formation of habits that determine one type or another of behavior.

Methods will depend on the purpose and content of upbringing. Upbringing techniques will be aimed at structuring the qualities of a harmonious personality. That is why taking into account the level of development of educators is an important condition for the effective use of upbringing methods. Students react differently to this or that educational influence. It depends on their particular characteristics, the level of upbringing, to what extent the methods of upbringing are chosen appropriately and efficiently, and skillfully applied. The correct choice of upbringing methods will help to increase the self-education activity of students in the positive solution of upbringing tasks. For example, in the process of working with first graders, the teacher uses a method of explaining the rules of behavior of students, the importance of having a clear agenda in them, the need for students to follow a strict order when teaching students labor activity new to them. Along with the explanation, it is practiced to get into the classroom correctly, greet them with teachers and students, maintain discipline. Together with this, the first graders are accustomed to the above processes during class. In the process, the positive work they have done, the results of the training work, are encouraged. It turns out that the teacher uses different methods and techniques when conducting the upbringing process with students. The variety of training methods indicates the need to divide them into types, classify them. Therefore, it is possible to divide them into groups, taking into account their individual characteristics. Every teacher (educator) who wants to achieve educational results, it is advisable to carefully master the methods of upbringing and their essence.

Training methods

1. Techniques that serve to shape social awareness
2. Methods of training in habituation and activity.
3. Methods of promotion and punishment in education

The task of the methods of the first group is to give the social consciousness of the student an understanding and knowledge of the rules and norms of life, morality, working relationships. In the process of upbringing, these rules and norms become the beliefs, beliefs and life views of the individual. This group includes spiritual, moral, aesthetic, ideological, legal, physical, environmental, economic, etc. content conversations as well as sampling techniques can be included. With the help of the methods of the second group, the reader forms habits related to spiritual content. In the behavior of the reader, in accordance with the content of social education, on the basis of spiritual habits, it is composed on the ground of activity.

Activity is an important resource enriching students with experience of social attitudes and social behavior. Among the methods of the second group, the method of pedagogical demand is significant. Pedagogical demand can be the fulfillment of various tasks, that is, the expression of the norm of social behavior, the implementation of a specific task that is

necessary to be performed by participating in one or another activity, the motivation for carrying out one or another action.

Requirements can be made directly or indirectly. Indirect requirements will be in the form of a strict command or instruction, performance, guide description. Indirect requirements are manifested in the form of advice, please, reproach, interest in their activities, provided that they arouse a feeling of forgiveness, aspiration. Requirements imply the presence in the reader of one degree or another of consciousness, foundation, purpose and faith. At the same time, the teacher must firmly attach importance to the norm of the requirements imposed on students.

In the process of useful activities and specially organized tasks, positive behavior and characters are taught.

Teaching is an activity that encourages various actions, organized practical activities, organized by students in a planned and systematic way, with the aim of transforming social behavior into their usual form.

Teaching is considered an effective tool at all stages of student education and development. Exercise in activities is the focus on the upbringing of labor, social activities, team activities and mutual habits. Exercise is in close contact with teaching. If on the basis of training lies the occupation of the child's activity process, then the activity of training is of particular importance for the individual. While training relies on teaching, many bora control repetition, reinforcement, and refinement, which remain the basis of Bora-bora social behavior.

In educational practice, it is often necessary to bring up special pedagogical situations, in which it will be possible to independently choose. In pedagogical situations, conditions are created in which students must change their opinion and behavior again.

Among the methods of the second group, the competition is a necessary and important quality of improving the effectiveness of methods for organizing practical activities of students. Promotes the development of activity and creativity of students in all areas of competition activity, directs the activities of the team of students to a specific goal. When the competition is organized correctly, a sense of community is successfully formed, discipline and student organization are strengthened.

In a separate type of competition, it is also organized in a systematic way: best class, best group, best team, best school, etc.

In the process of upbringing, it is important to achieve that students themselves organize the competition on the basis of initiative and enthusiasm, develop its conditions and indicators. It is also necessary to take care of the overall success of the team, the fulfillment of the accepted obligation, ensuring that the results of the competition are reflected in the stands. It is not advisable to organize the competition for official information. Public opinion remains an important foundation of competition activities.

Methods of the third group include such methods that are used to stimulate positive behavior in educators, correct or prevent negative traits, and directly influence their feelings and goals. This group includes techniques such as stimulation and punishment.

4. The role of aphorisms in education

The upbringing of the sign has long been of interest to man. This was particularly prominent in the pandetas associated with the name of Plato and Aristotle, prominent thinkers of Greece. In particular, in the Eastern countries, Plato's exhortations to Aristotle, and Aristotle's admonitions and Wills to Alexander are scattered as a whole work. Arastu says that the educator himself was brought up, possessed of human qualities-besides these, works such as "Rushnoinoma" on ethics and education, "Qobusnoma" Fariddin attor's "Pandnoma", O'bayd Zakoniy's "Sad pand" are common in Eastern countries. In the early Middle Ages, the treatises of Arastu and his followers were translated into Arabic, and their teachings were studied and enriched by Al-Kindiy, Farabi, Beruniy, Ibn Sino, Umar Khayyam, Nasriddin Tusi, Jomiy, Navoi and other Eastern philosophers.

Therefore, the role of the example is incomparable in the fact that the maturation and corresponding worldview of our today's youth regularly improves and develops. This, in turn, guarantees the preparation of conscious members of the creators of a free and prosperous homeland, a free and prosperous life.

5. Methods of promotion and punishment in education

Incentive methods-provide for a positive assessment of the actions of students. Stimulation generates experiences of joy, satisfaction, satisfaction, gives refreshment and enthusiasm, strengthens confidence in one's own strength, stimulates positive behavior, increases responsibility for one's activities and behavior. Incentive techniques are diverse and include approval, entertainment, encouragement, confidence, recording, verbal and written thanks, rewarding, etc.

Incentives should be applied taking into account pedagogical requirements. Any incentive must be in accordance with the student's truly outstanding services to the team. At the time of promotion, it is necessary to take into account the individual characteristics of the student, his place in the team, and he should not be in a row. Excessive praise-comparison towards the team-loosening exactingness, these are the reasons for the emergence of man-maniac, selfish qualities in the reader. In the organization of the incentive, along with the success of the student, it is also required to take into account his place in the team, his moral image, as well as the opinion of the team regarding Labor, team assignments, the attitude of the team to himself.

Punitive methods are negative assessments of student behavior and activities. Punishment represents the discussion of activities and behavior opposite to moral standards. Punishing can prevent inappropriate behavior, correct morality, shame in front of the team, arouse the feeling of being a sinner. Methods of punishment by or based on the support of the team are also hilma-different, which include reprimand, coagulation, embarrassment, reddening behaviors among the team, exclusion from certain activities, etc. Punishment is also necessary to follow pedagogical requirements. The punishment given is purposeful and should be given to the fault of the students, depending on their negative behavior. The reasons for negative behavior in the course of punishment should be taken into account the harm it causes to the team, the personal characteristics of the student. Punishment should not come from the interests of the student or serve for him. Punishment can also be given by the team. In all cases, the reader should not be physically and mentally tormented, bullied, slammed into the ground, disdained.

Conclusion

Today, special attention is paid to the use of information and technical means in the educational process. The purposeful and effective use of them leads to the spiritual maturation of students. The methods used by the teacher are also important in the organization of the educational process, which are determined by the tasks of educating the younger generation, which are put before educational institutions by a social society, in every possible way as a harmonious, free, creative, independent owner of thought. Training methods are divided into three groups according to their mutual aspects. Methods of educational tools used in the process of upbringing serve to strengthen the importance.

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